

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01**Topic:** HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-12**Type of action:** HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions

Project website

Deliverable: 8.3

Reference task:

Level of dissemination of the deliverable:

WP	8
Authors (partner)	EFFoST
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Revised by	

Abstract (summary of deliverable):

This document is aiming to describe the development of the project website and its contents.

Website

The CATALYSE project website will form a core component of both internal and external communication. An attractive website design will be an integral part of the professional presentation of CATALYSE. The website will outline the core objectives of the project and provide updates on activities and successes, as well as up-to-date information about the project for the general public. The website will be the platform for communicating the CATALYSE results, featuring links to the partner websites, project updates, news articles, events, social media widgets and contact information. Multimedia content will include video and animations, which will also be published on open platforms such as YouTube.

The project website will be the primary interface i) to facilitate interactions between partners and stakeholders in the CATALYSE CoP (WP4), ii) to find information in the area of food safety in the CATALYSE database (WP3), and iii) to access already available and new developed education materials (WP6). Once these functionalities are active, the website will facilitate interaction with the database (WP3) and the CoP (WP4), and include a download area with all promotional material, public deliverables and a calendar with relevant events, and links to open data and publications.

Delivered in M6, the CATALYSE website is hosted at www.thecatalyseproject.eu and contains the following menu and features that are subject to change/adaptation as the project progresses and upon suggestion by the partners and EFOST.

0. HOMEPAGE
 - a. Project logo / image / tagline + call to action 'Discover the project',
 - b. Sliding menu providing opportunity to highlight specific deliverables, reports, tools or events,
1. WHAT WE DO
 - a. The project,
 - b. Objectives,
 - c. Methodology,
 - d. Target groups,
 - e. Stakeholder Board,
2. CONSORTIUM
 - a. Project partners,
 - b. Associated partners,
 - c. Scientific Advisory Board,

3. NEWSROOM
 - a. News,
 - b. Events,
4. RESOURCES
 - a. Scientific publications,
 - b. Newsletters,
 - c. Press releases,
5. Contact us
6. Join our community

The webpage will feature data from the project and information about the scientific coordinators. Additionally, users will have easy options to sign up as members of the Community of Practice and to subscribe to the four-monthly newsletter. Direct links to social media platforms (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) will be provided.

The website is GDPR-compliant, and all visitors will be able to read the privacy policy. The website's design structure was presented to the partners in June 2024 and is continuously updated throughout the project's duration. EFFoST is exploring the option of adopting Matomo as a tracking platform for website analytics.

